

Synthesis of 2'-(3''-Pyridyl)- γ -Pyrano-Coumarins and 3'-Hydroxy-2'-(3''-Pyridyl)- γ -Pyrano-Coumarins

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A few 2'-(3''-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins (IVa-c) and 3'-hydroxy-2'-(3''-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins (Va-c) were synthesised from *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins.

COUMARINS, chalcones, 1,3-propanediones and chromones are known to possess physiological activities¹⁻³. Khellin—a furanochromone—has well-spasmodic properties¹¹⁻¹⁹. In view of this, the synthesis of γ -pyrano-coumarins was undertaken with the expectation that replacement of the furan ring by pyrone ring and a pyridyl group at 2' position will modify the activity of khellin itself.

Substituted *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins used as starting materials in this work, were prepared by the methods reported in literature²⁰⁻²¹.

Following *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins were used.

I. 7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin²⁰⁻²¹ ;
II. 7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-6-ethyl-4-methyl-coumarin²⁰⁻²⁴ ;
III. 7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin²⁵ ;
IV. 5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl-coumarin²⁶ and V. 5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,7-dimethyl-coumarin²⁰⁻²⁷.

The base-catalysed condensation of the above *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins with pyridine-3-aldehydes yielded prop-1-ene-3-ones(I). I underwent oxidative ring closure with SeO₂ in presence of amyl alcohol to form the corresponding 2-(3'' pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-(7,8) coumarins (IVa), 2'-(3''-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-(7,6) coumarins (IVb) and 2'-(3''-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-(5,6) coumarins (IVc).

The formation of γ -pyrano-coumarins was confirmed by synthesising these compounds by an alternative route. *o*-Hydroxy acetyl coumarins on treatment with nicotiny chloride yielded esters(II) which were converted into the corresponding 1,3-propanediones(III) by Baker-Venkatraman transformation. The cyclization of 1,3-propanediones afforded the corresponding γ -pyrano-coumarins (IVa-c). The identity of these compounds was proved by taking their mixed melting points which showed no depression.

The prop-1-ene-3-ones(I) under Algar-Flynn-Oyamada reaction conditions gave the corresponding 3'-hydroxy-2'-(3''-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins (Va-c). The physical data of I, II, III, IV and V is given in Table 1.

Physiological activity : 3-Pyridyl-prop-1-ene-3-6'-(4'-methyl-5'-hydroxy 7'-ethyl-coumarino)-one, 3-pyridyl-propan-1-ene-3-6'-(4' methyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarino)-one, showed activity.

o-Hydroxy acetyl coumarins were prepared by earlier known methods⁴⁻⁹.

General procedures for the preparation of

Prop-1-ene-3-ones(I) : To a solution of pyridine-3-aldehyde (0.3 mole) and hydroxy-acetyl coumarin (0.2 mole) in ethanol (30 ml), 50% solution of potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was added dropwise with mechanical stirring and maintaining the temperature below 25°. The mixture was stirred

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-3'-PYRIDYL-3-(SUBSTITUTED COUMARYL)-PROP-1-ENE-3-ONES(I), o-(3'-PYRIDILOXY)-ACETYL-COUMARINS(II), 1-(3'-PYRIDYL)-3-(SUBSTITUTED COUMARYL)-PROPANE-1,3-DIONES(III), 2'-(3'-PYRIDYL)-PYRANO-COUMARINS(IV) AND 3'-HYDROXY-2'-(3'-PYRIDYL)-PYRANO-COUMARINS(V)

Sl. No.	o-Hydroxy-acetyl coumarins used	Corresponding Compound									
		I*		II*		III*		IV*		V*	
		m.p.	Yield %	m.p.	Yield %	m.p.	Yield %	m.p.	Yield %	m.p.	Yield %
(1)	7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl 4-methyl coumarin	158 ^d	70	187 ^c	90	115 ^d	50	above 360 ^g	30	224 ^e	60
(2)	7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-6-ethyl-4-methyl coumarin	151 ^f	90	158 ^b	70	214 ^a	70	250 ^g	(40) 80	271 ^a	60
(3)	7-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl coumarin	189 ^d	50	171 ^c	70	198 ^c	80	256 ^g	(80) 20	above 360 ^b	30
(4)	5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methyl coumarin	198 ^c	40	162 ^b	60	169 ^f	50	222 ^g	(30) 20	218 ^e	20
(5)	5-Hydroxy-6-acetyl-4,7-dimethyl coumarin	199 ^f	40	220 ^b	40	164 ^d	60	220 ^g	(40) 40	193 ^a	50

* All compounds showed satisfactory C and H analyses.

- a : Crystallised from ethanol
 b : Crystallised from 40% acetic acid
 c : Crystallised from 50% acetic acid
 d : Crystallised from 60% acetic acid
 e : Crystallised from 70% acetic acid
 f : Crystallised from 80% acetic acid
 g : Crystallised from dioxane.

for 3 hrs and then poured over crushed ice containing sufficient quantity of acetic acid. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with NaHCO₃ solution (5%) and finally with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

2'-(3"-Pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins(IV) : A mixture of prop-1-ene-3-one (0.003 mole), SeO₂ (1 g) and amyl alcohol (14 ml) was refluxed for 10 hrs. The hot solution was filtered and amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The resulting solid was crystallised from a proper solvent.

3'-Hydroxy-2'-(3"-pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins(V) : To an ice-cold mixture of prop-1-ene-3-one (0.0014 mole) in methanol (15 ml) and sodium hydroxide solution (16%, 2 ml), H₂O₂ (15%, 2 ml) was added dropwise. The mixture was left in an ice-chest for 24 hrs and then filtered. The alkaline filtrate was acidified and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

Esters(II) : To an ice-cold mixture of o-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarin (0.035 mole) and dry pyridine (10 ml), nicotyl chloride (0.04 mole) was added slowly with stirring. The mixture was stirred further for 7 hrs at room temperature and then poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with 2% sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from a proper solvent.

1, 3-Propanediones(III) : The mixture of ester (0.045 mole), dry pyridine (15 ml), dry powdered KOH (3.4 g) was stirred vigorously for 6 hrs. It was poured over crushed ice and acidified with acetic acid. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

2'-(3"-Pyridyl)- γ -pyrano-coumarins(IV) : Conc. H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was added to an ice-cold solution of 1,3-propanedione (0.04 mole) in chloroform (40 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature and poured over ice-water. It was then made alkaline with conc. sodium hydroxide solution. The organic layer was separated and γ -pyrano-coumarin was isolated by the evaporation of chloroform. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from a proper solvent.

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